

The use of artificial neural network (ANN) for rapid quantification of morphological alteration of Red Blood Cell[†]

Sayari Ghosh^a, Raghendra Mishra^b, Debasish Sarkar^a, Roshnara Mishra^b and Dulal C. Mukherjee^{*c}

^aDepartment of Chemical Engineering, University of Calcutta, Kolkata-700 009, India

^bDepartment of Physiology, University of Calcutta, Kolkata-700 009, India

^cDepartment of Chemistry, Heritage Institute of Technology, Kolkata-700 107, India

E-mail : dcm_chem@yahoo.co.in

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Abstract : The biconcave shape and corresponding deformability of human RBC is an essential biological function. This property can be significantly altered by various pathophysiological conditions leading to the generation of morphological derivatives with abnormal shapes. Hence measuring the population morphology of blood samples, hold the key to understand the characteristics of different diseases. However the morphological studies, despite their potential clinical application, are compromised due to lack of rapid and accurate technique. In this study, we have precisely simulated the shape quantifying parameter of a RBC population, known as Morphological Index (MI) from the respective light scattering data obtained from a flow cytometer. Accordingly, the significant distribution parameters of forward and side scatter data were chosen to formulate a sophisticated artificial neural network (ANN) model with MI as output. The analysis yields a three layered network with 10 neurons in the hidden layer with MI as the sole output ($R^2 = 0.982$). Moreover, for a set of 10 samples exclusive to model formulation, the model was observed to predict MI with commendable accuracy ($R^2 = 0.99$). The proposed method was verified to rapid, cost effective and clinically simple for the measurement of population morphology of RBC.

Keywords : Morphology, red blood cell, flow cytometry, microscopy, artificial neural network.

Introduction

RBC morphology plays a very important role in the diagnosis of the diseases like Sickle cell anemia, Thalassemia, Hereditary Spherocytosis, Hereditary Elliptocytosis etc. Besides it becomes one of the subjects of interest in the field of neonatology, cytoskeletal and membrane composition studies, in drug interactions studies for research, clinical and screening purpose¹. Normally RBC has a biconcave disc like structure, known as discocyte and blessed with flexibility to pass through any narrow blood vessels. But sometimes, the shape of RBC is altered under some genetic abnormalities and some pathological conditions or by parasitic infestations. Thereby, deformed RBC appear in blood. Morphological disorder is mainly characterized by the changes in bonding of cytoskeletal protein network (spectrin) with the phospholipids bilayer, present in the Red Blood Cell membrane. The membrane consist of three layers² : at first a periph-

eral carbohydrate-rich layer, then the phospholipid bilayer (thickness 4–5 nm), surrounded with transmembrane proteins, and the third one is a 2-D triangular mesh-like spectrin cytoskeleton network bonded with the surface bilayers as shown in the Fig. 1. The bonding of these two is restricted by ATP³. Actually the intricate properties of the lipid bilayer and spectrin network is the main executor of its regular healthy discocyte shape and also responsible for elastic and biorheological properties of RBC.

Mainly spectrin network determines the shear elastic properties of the RBC. The spectrin network and lipid bilayer are linked via integral (Band 3, Glycophorin, Aquaporin) and peripheral proteins (ankrin, protein 4.1, protein 4.2, aldolase, glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase, phosphofructokinase, deoxyhemoglobin, p72syk, Protein tyrosine kinase, and hemichromes), where band 3 protein act as a cytoplasmic domain⁴. Basic unit is a hexagonal lattice with 6 spectrin molecules. Each linked

[†]In honor of Professor K. C. Joshi on the occasion of his 88th birthday.

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of normal RBC (right insert shows the two dimensional connectivity of spectrin network).

to the next complex by multiple spectrin tetramers. Ankyrin links the lipid bilayer to membrane skeleton via interaction with band 3. Both the monomer stabilize a symmetric dimer of band 3, created by interlocked dimerization arms. A larger secondary protein binding domain with an $\alpha 1$ b-fold is linked to each subunit⁴. Additionally, band 3 includes different glycolytic enzymes and carbonic anhydrase to form a composite known as ‘metabolon’, which is amendable for red cell metabolism and also act as an ion and gas transport function⁵. Recently, morphological studies of RBC have proved the importance in routine clinical analysis⁶. But the conventional microscopic analysis, accessible for RBC morphological study, is prone to personal bias, costly man-hour. For microscopic analysis, Morphological Index (MI) can be defined as a number fraction weighted average of Morphological Score (MS) ($MI = \sum x_i MS_i$, where x_i be the number fraction of i -th derivative)⁷, whereas the MS is a morphological quantifier of the different shape derivatives like discocytes echinocytes, stomatocytes, spherocytes etc. Therefore, manual counting of different shape derivatives is necessary for the determination of x_i and hence MI. As a result there is always a probability of getting deviant MI, which may lead to wrong diagnosis. These restrictions have compelled to take help of automation by quantifying size or rheological characters of RBC in automated cell counters or laser diffractometers, ektacytometer, Rayleigh scattering, and other methods⁷⁻¹¹.

Over the last two decades flow cytometry has been recognized as an alternative of microscopy particularly for the analysis of large cell populations¹². Moreover a

standard cytometric method can handle large throughput much more efficiently compared to microscopy. In a standard flow cytometer, one can readily obtain the size information based small angle/forward scatter (FSC) signal along with surface granularity dependent orthogonal/side scatter (SSC) data of a cell population. In addition to simple spherical and sphere perturbed derivative shapes, cytometric studies with mean non-spherical shaped particle population largely centered on RBC and sperm cell. Though the scattering profile can be simulated for spherical and near spherical shapes, primarily by using Finite Difference Time Domain (FDTD) method¹³⁻¹⁷, for non-spherical topology the exact functional relation between the scattering data and the mean shape related geometry is still largely unknown. The present work has been undertaken in an attempt to develop a functional relation between the flow cytometric data and MI (the shape quantifier) of a random RBC population. To develop such a functional model the well known black box modeling technique of artificial neural network (ANN) was used. The proposed model was validated using a completely new set of experimental data spanning over the full range of MI data.

Materials and method :

Sample preparation :

At first we have collected blood from healthy volunteers (Male-6, female-4; Age : 28 ± 2 years; body weight : 68.8 ± 11.68 kg; resting heart rate : 74.6 ± 4.45 beats/minute; Systolic pressure : 125.8 ± 4.57 mm Hg and diastolic pressure : 84.2 ± 3.33 mm Hg; data represented as mean \pm standard deviation). To generate mixed

population of morphologically altered RBC cells, the samples were treated with different poikilocytic agents in different doses randomly, following the new guideline for hemorheological laboratory techniques¹⁸. For echinocytosis and stomatocytosis to happen, Eosin-5-maelimide¹⁹ (E5M; 1–3 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$ packed cell) and *Naja kaouthia* snake venom²⁰ (0.5–2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ whole blood) were used respectively as poikilocytic agents. It is to be noted that for model formulation 65 such samples were used, which were analyzed by flow cytometry and microscopy simultaneously. Additionally a new set of 10 samples which includes patient blood sample was used to validate the proposed model.

Flow cytometry :

Flow cytometric analyses were performed on a BD FACS Aria III using BD FACS Diva software for acquisition and analysis. The FSC channel was set on linear scale and the SSC channel on logarithmic scale. A total number of 30,000 events were recorded for each sample. As usual, the height, width and area parameter of the voltage pulse were recorded and the corresponding distributions were generated by the inbuilt software.

Confocal imaging and MI evaluation :

BD pathway 855 was used for imaging of RBC populations. The RBCs were seeded into a 96 well bio-imaging plate and incubated on stage for 15 min to allow the cells to settle. Nipkow spinning disc based confocal images were captured by a CCD camera. A 3×3 confocal stacked montage image was captured for each well and the number fractions (x_i) of the major shape derivatives were calculated. The concept of Morphological Score (MS) was first introduced by Besis²¹. Since then the scoring

has been modified and personalized for particular works. Usually a discocyte has the score of zero. Species with spiculation has positive values ascertained to them, so naturally species with invagination has negative score. The highest scores positive as well as negative, were assigned to the spherocytic RBC population obtained through either via echinocytosis or stomatocytosis respectively. The reported MS range varies from $[-1, +1]$ to $[-5, +5]$. Relevant work in this field also indicate that stomatocytosis and echinocytosis are mutually exclusive²². So that there is no scope of mutual cancellation of $\{x_i\text{MS}_i\}$ terms in the evaluation of MI.

For the present study we have chosen the MS range to be $[-0.1, +0.1]$, adequate to uniformly distribute the five different morphological derivatives of RBC. As per convention, we have chosen $\text{MS} = 0$ for discocyte, $\text{MS} = +1.0$ for spherocyte via echinocytic pathway, $\text{MS} = -1.0$ spherocytic pathway. The intermediate population in both pathways were assigned with $\text{MS} = \pm 0.5$. The corresponding scale is shown in Fig. 2. It is to be noted that the present scoring system is totally empirical as others. However, by the corresponding signs echinocytic population could be differential from the stomatocytic population. Thereafter MI values of control and poikilocytic agent treated samples were calculated from Z stacked confocal microscopic images.

Artificial Neural Network (ANN) methodology :

Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) are recognized as an alternative to the standard physical models, particularly in cases where the underlying physics of the system is too complex to analyze. The inspiration of using neural networks came from the biological structure of human brain^{23,24}. For scientific and engineering purpose, ANN

Fig. 2. The morphological scale adopted for the present study.

model may be regarded as a “black box”, which accepts the input vector and generates the desired output, processing the input through a group of functional elements, known as ‘neurons’ or ‘nodes’. The most used ANN architecture is the multilayer perceptron (MLP) in which nodes are organized in at least three layers, input, hidden and output. Because of the unidirectionality of connections between different nodes from input to hidden to output, the network is regarded as feed forward type. With certain nonlinear transfer functions associated to the neurons of hidden and output layers (f_h and f_o respectively), the output (\hat{y}) may be expressed as

$$\hat{y} = f_o[\sum_{j=0}^m w_{j0} f_h(\sum_{i=1}^n w_{ij} x_i)] \quad (1)$$

where $X = [X_1, \dots, x_n]^T$ is the input vector, w_{ij} is the weight associated to input i with hidden neuron j and w_{j0} is the weight connecting hidden neuron j with output. Here n is the number of inputs and m is the number of hidden neurons. For the present study we have used feed forward MLP-ANN architecture as it was reported by Cybenko²⁵ that a feed forward MLP-ANN with one hidden layer of sigmoid or hyperbolic tangent functions connected to one output layer of linear transfer function is capable of simulating any continuous function. Out of twelve standard transfer functions, tan-sigmoid transfer function was chosen because the corresponding range of the function $\Rightarrow [-1, 1]$ is exactly consistent with the theoretical range of Morphological Index (MI). For network training, the well known back propagation (BP) method was used. Back propagation method operates in two sequential phases; one is the training phase whereas the other one is the testing (recall) phase. The training is guided by specifying the target output of the network to each training input followed by its comparison with the actual output. The error propagates backward from output to hidden layers up to the input layer with weight coefficients (w_{j0} or w_{ij}) remaining unchanged. Next the weight coefficients are revised based on the error gradient until and unless some stop criterion (number of iteration or maximum permissible error threshold) is satisfied. There are several algorithms available to implement BP. Because of the conjugate qualities of Newton algorithm (speed) and steepest descent method (stability), the well known Levenberg-Marquart algorithm (LMA)²⁶ was chosen for the present study.

The total data set (60 samples) was divided into training (35), validation (10) and test (15). As mentioned previously, the model validity was further checked by using a completely new subset of 10 test data comparing of control and patient blood samples. Neural Network toolbox V4.0 of MATLAB software package was used for the present work.

Results and discussion

Light scattering of particles is a standard technique to extract information regarding their shape, size and immunophenotyping. Till date, spherical or near spherical particles were dealt with major interest due to its even scattering pattern. Scattering from non spherical particles exhibit complex asymmetric profile and thus is largely unattained. Due to its discoid shape and presence of centre pallor, scattering from RBC varies largely and becomes hard to interpret quantitatively. Moreover, under different pathological conditions complex shape derivatives like echinocyte, stomatocytes etc. evolve, which make the analysis further complicated. Based on the scoring system adopted and customized for the present work, we have tried to correlate the statistical parameters of flow cytometry (distribution statistics of height, width and area of FSC and SSC signals for a sample) to MI via a feed forward MLP neural network. For this purpose, the primary task was to identify the minimum number of mutually independent parameters, which can be best correlated to the MI value of corresponding sample. However, the choice must not be redundant in order to avoid the subsequent complication in the ANN model. Fig. 3 represents the distributions of height, width and area of both FSC and SSC for three different samples with (I) discocyte, (II) echinocyte and (III) stomatocyte as major shape derivative respectively. The figure clearly indicates that both area and height distributions of FSC as well as SSC either show a negative shouldering or a bimodality, whereas the width distributions are perfectly unimodal for all cases. Accordingly, the width distribution parameters were chosen to be the most suitable group for the functional relation with MI as response. Based on the results of univariate analysis, reported in our previous study¹, four distribution parameters of width were selected for ANN model. The best correlated width parameters are (i) Median of FSC width (X_1), (ii) Median of SSC width (X_2), (iii) Ro-

Fig. 3. Determination of red blood cell morphology by analyzing flow cytometric scattering. Photomicrograph and flow cytometric scatter analysis of normal and poikilocytic agent treated population of RBCs, the name given are the major cell population in the sample. (I-a) Discocytic population, (II-a) Echinocytic population, (III-a) Stomatocytic population. Microscopy was performed by BD pathway (in PBS, Plan Apochromat objective, 60 × magnification, NA = 0.95, transmission mode) and photomicrograph were used for morphological scoring of RBC and calculation of the morphological index of different groups. Sample gating was done manually using the area versus height data of normal control samples (subset b) for doublet discrimination and same gate was used to analyse the normal and treated RBC. Flowcytometric analysis of different poikilocytic populations were represented in dot plots (subset c). The FSC area vs SSC area dot plot showed tapering in echinocytic poikilocytes population which became a sculptured woodpecker like structure in stomatocytic poikilocytes. FSC and SSC histograms of area, height and width (subset d) of FSC and SSC respectively were depicted where the distribution width showed to be decreased with the loss of discocytic populations.

bust coefficient variance of FSC width (X_3) and (iv) Robust coefficient of variance of SSC width (X_4) distribution. The corresponding MI was set as target. Therefore the functional form becomes

$$MI = f(X), \text{ where } X = [X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4]^T \quad (2)$$

To ensure the importance of the input variables, principal

component analysis (PCA) was carried out. It was observed that all the chosen variables are important.

Calculation of MI :

The MI of the samples ranged from -0.64 to 0.69, where the sign implies the presence of stomatocyte and echinocyte respectively. The present experimental range

covers almost entire span practicable. The theoretical range of -1 to $+1$ is never achievable in practice because the senescent RBC are prone to lysis as they could not withstand any physical or chemical changes and therefore clears from the system. Also the donor blood contains a mixture younger and older RBCs, which show the variable responses to the same poikilocytic agents resulting in a mixed population. For each samples, the MI was calculated from the respective confocal image with a field of more than 200 cells. All the counting experiments were repeated thrice to avoid any possible error.

Flow cytometry and scatter plot analysis :

The raw scatter plot of FSC vs SSC data was first gated to avoid the noise caused by cell debris as well as RBC doublets. The manually drawn gates, as shown in Fig. 3 isolate the region of scatter plot for closer investigation and data refinement; the refined contour of FSC vs SSC data of area distribution exhibits a more symmetric structure from discocyte to echinocyte to stomatocyte population. Over the gated region, all the three distribution pattern of area, height and width of each sample were acquired and analyzed with flow Diva (version 6.1.3) software. The central tendencies and dispersion statistics were also calculated for all the samples.

Configuration of ANN and model validation :

The optimum number of neurons was determined based on the minimum value of mean square error (MSE) of the training and the validation set. The optimization was carried out using LMA as a training algorithm and varying neuron number in the range of 1–20. Fig. 4 shows the trend of MSE with the number of neurons. MSE was used in the hidden layer and reduced to 0.018 when the 10 number of neurons were used. Beyond 10, MSE was observed to level off to 0.018. Therefore 10 neurons were selected as the optimum number for the present network. Fig. 5 represents the optimized ANN architecture with tangent sigmoid function at hidden layers with 10 neurons and linear function at output layer. As mentioned previously altogether 60 data sets were used for training, validation and testing the ANN model. Fig. 6 shows the comparison between actual MI and predicted MI values for training (6.I), validation (6.II), testing (6.III) and overall (6.IV) separately. The Fig. 6.IV, which incorporates all data points, contains two lines. The dotted line makes the perfect fit : actual = predicted ($y = x$), whereas the solid line represents the best fit between the actual and the predicted MI values of the present study. The equation of the best fit line is

$$y = (1.05)x + 0.051 \quad (3)$$

Fig. 4. Relation between the number of neurons and MSE.

Fig. 5. Optimized ANN architecture with tangent sigmoid function at hidden layers with 10 neurons and linear function at output layer.

The correlation coefficient (R^2) and MSE values are 0.982 and 0.018 respectively. It is to be noted that, the present correlation coefficient ($= 0.982$) is higher than the highest correlation coefficient obtained in the previously reported multivariable regression analysis ($= 0.96$).

In addition to model testing with inbuilt data, the proposed model was further validated using a new set of experimental data, exclusive to model formulation. The new set comprises of 10 samples, which are mostly patient blood in addition to a single control sample. The corresponding parity diagram is shown in Fig. 7. High correlation coefficient ($R^2 = 0.99$) clearly indicates the general validity of the proposed model.

Fig. 6. Comparison between actual MI and predicted MI values for training (6.I), validation (6.II), testing (6.III) and overall data set (6.IV).

Fig. 7. Parity diagram for actual vs predicted MI for model formulation exclusive sample data set.

Discussion

Deviations from regular biconcave shape are significant indicator of RBC pathology. The reasons may be genetic, infectious or chemical imbalance. For example, spherocytes or near spherical shape derivatives of RBC impede blood flow resulting in anemia, fatigue and splenomegaly²⁷. Therefore RBC deformability is regarded as a key to circulation. The biconcave shape of discocyte and related elastic properties, necessary for large, reversible elastic deformation during microcirculation in small capillaries are maintained by a variety of factors. This includes membrane lipid-lipid, lipid-protein as well as protein-protein interactions²⁸. Poikilocytic changes involve alteration of lipid raft and/or changes in interactions between anchoring and cytoskeletal proteins. Recent finding²⁹ suggests that band 3 alterations can precede and regulate the area of the outer lipid raft, relative to inner one and thus leads to a change in membrane curvature. In addition to that, disruptions of vertical (connection of integral and peripheral protein to spectrin network) and horizontal (binding of two dimensional spectrin network) interactions are known to affect the spectrin network, which invariably causes morphological alterations. The mechanical integrity of the cell structure can be estimated by shear modulus and bending modulus³⁰.

From the experimentally measured data of these two parameters, Li *et al.* have established the biconcave shape to be the only feasible minimum energy configuration³¹. Neglecting the contribution of strain energy, the biconcave shape can also be achieved by minimization of bending energy³². In the hierarchy of low energy configurations, echinocyte, stomatocyte and spherocyte appears next to biconcave discocyte as stable shape derivatives. Recent studies also postulate three major factors that influence the structure and mechanical integrity of RBC morphology as (i) shear stress, (ii) nature of vertical interactions and (iii) metabolic activity arising out from chemical energy³³.

Now a day we have highlighted techniques for studying RBC deformability. Due to various test techniques developed in the last decade, our understandings on pathophysiology of RBC have been significantly improved. Recent advances have enabled the precise measurements of various biochemical properties of RBC under systematically controlled conditions that mimic complex *in vivo* physiological environments³⁴. However, in order to make a much broader impact the current throughput of cells must be enhanced to several folds, such that it becomes a routine pathology job. Several attempts were taken for this much desired rapid quantification using different techniques in different instrumental platform, of which automated cytometric analysis has its greater share. Use of scattering property to identify the RBC's morphological alteration was first initiated by Hoffman³⁵, who has used the variation property of Rayleigh scattering from a stirred suspension to describe the shape alteration of RBC. Later this technique was further reformed by several groups^{36,37} in order to extract a quasi-quantitative information about the shape and granularity. In our previous work¹, we have reported a multivariable quadratic regression model to correlate the representative scattering profiles directly to the MI value of the respective blood sample. The present work may be viewed as an extension of previous method replacing the crude regression technique by sophisticated MLP-ANN architecture. Improved correlation coefficient ($R^2 = 0.99$), compared to our previous work, establishes the gross validity of the proposed model in rapid and accurate quantification of MI.

Conclusion

A three-layer back propagation in neural network model is proposed to simulate the Morphological Index (MI), a quantifier of the mean population morphology of RBC from rapidly generable flow cytometric data. The architecture of the back propagation neural network leading to the smallest mean square error comprised of three layered ANN with tangent-sigmoid function at hidden layers with 10 neurons, and linear transfer function at output layer. Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm was chosen to train the network. ANN predicted MI values for 60 different samples were found to be in close agreement ($R^2 = 0.982$) with the experimental MI data obtained from confocal microscopy. Therefore, the proposed quantitative technique may be viewed as a novel pathological method, which may lead to the development of new diagnostic and treatment strategies for various RBC related disease.

Acknowledgement

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^aDepartment of Chemical Engineering, University of Calcutta, Kolkata-700 009, India

^bDepartment of Physiology, University of Calcutta, Kolkata-700 009, India

^cDepartment of Chemistry, Heritage Institute of Technology, Kolkata-700 107, India

E-mail : dcm_chem@yahoo.co.in

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Introduction

RBC morphology plays a very important role in the diagnosis of the diseases like Sick cell anemia, Thalassemia, Hereditary Spherocytosis, Hereditary Elliptocytosis etc. Besides it becomes one of the subjects of interest in the field of neonatology, cytoskeletal and membrane composition studies, in drug interactions studies for research, clinical and screening purpose¹. Normally RBC has a biconcave disc like structure, known as discocyte and blessed with flexibility to pass through any narrow blood vessels. But sometimes, the shape of RBC is altered under some genetic abnormalities and some pathological conditions or by parasitic infestations. Thereby, deformed RBC appear in blood. Morphological disorder is mainly characterized by the changes in bonding of cytoskeletal protein network (spectrin) with the phospholipids bilayer, present in the Red Blood Cell membrane. The membrane consist of three layers² : at first a periph-

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[†]In honor of Professor K. C. Joshi on the occasion of his 88th birthday.

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of normal RBC (right insert shows the two dimensional connectivity of spectrin network).

to the next complex by multiple spectrin tetramers. Ankyrin links the lipid bilayer to membrane skeleton via interaction with band 3. Both the monomer stabilize a symmetric dimer of band 3, created by interlocked dimerization arms. A larger secondary protein binding domain with an $\alpha 1$ b-fold is linked to each subunit⁴. Additionally, band 3 includes different glycolytic enzymes and carbonic anhydrase to form a composite known as ‘metabolon’, which is amendable for red cell metabolism and also act as an ion and gas transport function⁵. Recently, morphological studies of RBC have proved the importance in routine clinical analysis⁶. But the conventional microscopic analysis, accessible for RBC morphological study, is prone to personal bias, costly man-hour. For microscopic analysis, Morphological Index (MI) can be defined as a number fraction weighted average of Morphological Score (MS) ($MI = \sum x_i MS_i$, where x_i be the number fraction of i -th derivative)⁷, whereas the MS is a morphological quantifier of the different shape derivatives like discocytes echinocytes, stomatocytes, spherocytes etc. Therefore, manual counting of different shape derivatives is necessary for the determination of x_i and hence MI. As a result there is always a probability of getting deviant MI, which may lead to wrong diagnosis. These restrictions have compelled to take help of automation by quantifying size or rheological characters of RBC in automated cell counters or laser diffractometers, ektacytometer, Rayleigh scattering, and other methods⁷⁻¹¹.

Over the last two decades flow cytometry has been recognized as an alternative of microscopy particularly for the analysis of large cell populations¹². Moreover a

standard cytometric method can handle large throughput much more efficiently compared to microscopy. In a standard flow cytometer, one can readily obtain the size information based small angle/forward scatter (FSC) signal along with surface granularity dependent orthogonal/side scatter (SSC) data of a cell population. In addition to simple spherical and sphere perturbed derivative shapes, cytometric studies with mean non-spherical shaped particle population largely centered on RBC and sperm cell. Though the scattering profile can be simulated for spherical and near spherical shapes, primarily by using Finite Difference Time Domain (FDTD) method¹³⁻¹⁷, for non-spherical topology the exact functional relation between the scattering data and the mean shape related geometry is still largely unknown. The present work has been undertaken in an attempt to develop a functional relation between the flow cytometric data and MI (the shape quantifier) of a random RBC population. To develop such a functional model the well known black box modeling technique of artificial neural network (ANN) was used. The proposed model was validated using a completely new set of experimental data spanning over the full range of MI data.

Materials and method :

Sample preparation :

At first we have collected blood from healthy volunteers (Male-6, female-4; Age : 28 ± 2 years; body weight : 68.8 ± 11.68 kg; resting heart rate : 74.6 ± 4.45 beats/minute; Systolic pressure : 125.8 ± 4.57 mm Hg and diastolic pressure : 84.2 ± 3.33 mm Hg; data represented as mean \pm standard deviation). To generate mixed

population of morphologically altered RBC cells, the samples were treated with different poikilocytic agents in different doses randomly, following the new guideline for hemorheological laboratory techniques¹⁸. For echinocytosis and stomatocytosis to happen, Eosin-5-maelimide¹⁹ (E5M; 1–3 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$ packed cell) and *Naja kaouthia* snake venom²⁰ (0.5–2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ whole blood) were used respectively as poikilocytic agents. It is to be noted that for model formulation 65 such samples were used, which were analyzed by flow cytometry and microscopy simultaneously. Additionally a new set of 10 samples which includes patient blood sample was used to validate the proposed model.

Flow cytometry :

Flow cytometric analyses were performed on a BD FACS Aria III using BD FACS Diva software for acquisition and analysis. The FSC channel was set on linear scale and the SSC channel on logarithmic scale. A total number of 30,000 events were recorded for each sample. As usual, the height, width and area parameter of the voltage pulse were recorded and the corresponding distributions were generated by the inbuilt software.

Confocal imaging and MI evaluation :

BD pathway 855 was used for imaging of RBC populations. The RBCs were seeded into a 96 well bio-imaging plate and incubated on stage for 15 min to allow the cells to settle. Nipkow spinning disc based confocal images were captured by a CCD camera. A 3×3 confocal stacked montage image was captured for each well and the number fractions (x_i) of the major shape derivatives were calculated. The concept of Morphological Score (MS) was first introduced by Besis²¹. Since then the scoring

has been modified and personalized for particular works. Usually a discocyte has the score of zero. Species with spiculation has positive values ascertained to them, so naturally species with invagination has negative score. The highest scores positive as well as negative, were assigned to the spherocytic RBC population obtained through either via echinocytosis or stomatocytosis respectively. The reported MS range varies from $[-1, +1]$ to $[-5, +5]$. Relevant work in this field also indicate that stomatocytosis and echinocytosis are mutually exclusive²². So that there is no scope of mutual cancellation of $\{x_i\text{MS}_i\}$ terms in the evaluation of MI.

For the present study we have chosen the MS range to be $[-0.1, +0.1]$, adequate to uniformly distribute the five different morphological derivatives of RBC. As per convention, we have chosen $\text{MS} = 0$ for discocyte, $\text{MS} = +1.0$ for spherocyte via echinocytic pathway, $\text{MS} = -1.0$ spherocytic pathway. The intermediate population in both pathways were assigned with $\text{MS} = \pm 0.5$. The corresponding scale is shown in Fig. 2. It is to be noted that the present scoring system is totally empirical as others. However, by the corresponding signs ehinocytic population could be differential from the stomatocytic population. Thereafter MI values of control and poikilocytic agent treated samples were calculated from Z stacked confocal microscopic images.

Artificial Neural Network (ANN) methodology :

Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) are recognized as an alternative to the standard physical models, particularly in cases where the underlying physics of the system is too complex to analyze. The inspiration of using neural networks came from the biological structure of human brain^{23,24}. For scientific and engineering purpose, ANN

Fig. 2. The morphological scale adopted for the present study.

model may be regarded as a “black box”, which accepts the input vector and generates the desired output, processing the input through a group of functional elements, known as ‘neurons’ or ‘nodes’. The most used ANN architecture is the multilayer perceptron (MLP) in which nodes are organized in at least three layers, input, hidden and output. Because of the unidirectionality of connections between different nodes from input to hidden to output, the network is regarded as feed forward type. With certain nonlinear transfer functions associated to the neurons of hidden and output layers (f_h and f_o respectively), the output (\hat{y}) may be expressed as

$$\hat{y} = f_o[\sum_{j=0}^m w_{j0} f_h(\sum_{i=1}^n w_{ij} x_i)] \quad (1)$$

where $X = [X_1, \dots, x_n]^T$ is the input vector, w_{ij} is the weight associated to input i with hidden neuron j and w_{j0} is the weight connecting hidden neuron j with output. Here n is the number of inputs and m is the number of hidden neurons. For the present study we have used feed forward MLP-ANN architecture as it was reported by Cybenko²⁵ that a feed forward MLP-ANN with one hidden layer of sigmoid or hyperbolic tangent functions connected to one output layer of linear transfer function is capable of simulating any continuous function. Out of twelve standard transfer functions, tan-sigmoid transfer function was chosen because the corresponding range of the function $\Rightarrow [-1, 1]$ is exactly consistent with the theoretical range of Morphological Index (MI). For network training, the well known back propagation (BP) method was used. Back propagation method operates in two sequential phases; one is the training phase whereas the other one is the testing (recall) phase. The training is guided by specifying the target output of the network to each training input followed by its comparison with the actual output. The error propagates backward from output to hidden layers up to the input layer with weight coefficients (w_{j0} or w_{ij}) remaining unchanged. Next the weight coefficients are revised based on the error gradient until and unless some stop criterion (number of iteration or maximum permissible error threshold) is satisfied. There are several algorithms available to implement BP. Because of the conjugate qualities of Newton algorithm (speed) and steepest descent method (stability), the well known Levenberg-Marquart algorithm (LMA)²⁶ was chosen for the present study.

The total data set (60 samples) was divided into training (35), validation (10) and test (15). As mentioned previously, the model validity was further checked by using a completely new subset of 10 test data comparing of control and patient blood samples. Neural Network toolbox V4.0 of MATLAB software package was used for the present work.

Results and discussion

Light scattering of particles is a standard technique to extract information regarding their shape, size and immunophenotyping. Till date, spherical or near spherical particles were dealt with major interest due to its even scattering pattern. Scattering from non spherical particles exhibit complex asymmetric profile and thus is largely unattained. Due to its discoid shape and presence of centre pallor, scattering from RBC varies largely and becomes hard to interpret quantitatively. Moreover, under different pathological conditions complex shape derivatives like echinocyte, stomatocytes etc. evolve, which make the analysis further complicated. Based on the scoring system adopted and customized for the present work, we have tried to correlate the statistical parameters of flow cytometry (distribution statistics of height, width and area of FSC and SSC signals for a sample) to MI via a feed forward MLP neural network. For this purpose, the primary task was to identify the minimum number of mutually independent parameters, which can be best correlated to the MI value of corresponding sample. However, the choice must not be redundant in order to avoid the subsequent complication in the ANN model. Fig. 3 represents the distributions of height, width and area of both FSC and SSC for three different samples with (I) discocyte, (II) echinocyte and (III) stomatocyte as major shape derivative respectively. The figure clearly indicates that both area and height distributions of FSC as well as SSC either show a negative shouldering or a bimodality, whereas the width distributions are perfectly unimodal for all cases. Accordingly, the width distribution parameters were chosen to be the most suitable group for the functional relation with MI as response. Based on the results of univariate analysis, reported in our previous study¹, four distribution parameters of width were selected for ANN model. The best correlated width parameters are (i) Median of FSC width (X_1), (ii) Median of SSC width (X_2), (iii) Ro-

Fig. 3. Determination of red blood cell morphology by analyzing flow cytometric scattering. Photomicrograph and flow cytometric scatter analysis of normal and poikilocytic agent treated population of RBCs, the name given are the major cell population in the sample. (I-a) Discocytic population, (II-a) Echinocytic population, (III-a) Stomatocytic population. Microscopy was performed by BD pathway (in PBS, Plan Apochromat objective, 60 × magnification, NA = 0.95, transmission mode) and photomicrograph were used for morphological scoring of RBC and calculation of the morphological index of different groups. Sample gating was done manually using the area versus height data of normal control samples (subset b) for doublet discrimination and same gate was used to analyse the normal and treated RBC. Flowcytometric analysis of different poikilocytic populations were represented in dot plots (subset c). The FSC area vs SSC area dot plot showed tapering in echinocytic poikilocytes population which became a sculptured woodpecker like structure in stomatocytic poikilocytes. FSC and SSC histograms of area, height and width (subset d) of FSC and SSC respectively were depicted where the distribution width showed to be decreased with the loss of discocytic populations.

robust coefficient variance of FSC width (X_3) and (iv) Robust coefficient of variance of SSC width (X_4) distribution. The corresponding MI was set as target. Therefore the functional form becomes

$$MI = f(X), \text{ where } X = [X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4]^T \quad (2)$$

To ensure the importance of the input variables, principal

component analysis (PCA) was carried out. It was observed that all the chosen variables are important.

Calculation of MI :

The MI of the samples ranged from -0.64 to 0.69, where the sign implies the presence of stomatocyte and echinocyte respectively. The present experimental range

covers almost entire span practicable. The theoretical range of -1 to $+1$ is never achievable in practice because the senescent RBC are prone to lysis as they could not withstand any physical or chemical changes and therefore clears from the system. Also the donor blood contains a mixture younger and older RBCs, which show the variable responses to the same poikilocytic agents resulting in a mixed population. For each samples, the MI was calculated from the respective confocal image with a field of more than 200 cells. All the counting experiments were repeated thrice to avoid any possible error.

Flow cytometry and scatter plot analysis :

The raw scatter plot of FSC vs SSC data was first gated to avoid the noise caused by cell debris as well as RBC doublets. The manually drawn gates, as shown in Fig. 3 isolate the region of scatter plot for closer investigation and data refinement; the refined contour of FSC vs SSC data of area distribution exhibits a more symmetric structure from discocyte to echinocyte to stomatocyte population. Over the gated region, all the three distribution pattern of area, height and width of each sample were acquired and analyzed with flow Diva (version 6.1.3) software. The central tendencies and dispersion statistics were also calculated for all the samples.

Configuration of ANN and model validation :

The optimum number of neurons was determined based on the minimum value of mean square error (MSE) of the training and the validation set. The optimization was carried out using LMA as a training algorithm and varying neuron number in the range of 1–20. Fig. 4 shows the trend of MSE with the number of neurons. MSE was used in the hidden layer and reduced to 0.018 when the 10 number of neurons were used. Beyond 10, MSE was observed to level off to 0.018. Therefore 10 neurons were selected as the optimum number for the present network. Fig. 5 represents the optimized ANN architecture with tangent sigmoid function at hidden layers with 10 neurons and linear function at output layer. As mentioned previously altogether 60 data sets were used for training, validation and testing the ANN model. Fig. 6 shows the comparison between actual MI and predicted MI values for training (6.I), validation (6.II), testing (6.III) and overall (6.IV) separately. The Fig. 6.IV, which incorporates all data points, contains two lines. The dotted line makes the perfect fit : actual = predicted ($y = x$), whereas the solid line represents the best fit between the actual and the predicted MI values of the present study. The equation of the best fit line is

$$y = (1.05)x + 0.051 \quad (3)$$

Fig. 4. Relation between the number of neurons and MSE.

Fig. 5. Optimized ANN architecture with tangent sigmoid function at hidden layers with 10 neurons and linear function at output layer.

The correlation coefficient (R^2) and MSE values are 0.982 and 0.018 respectively. It is to be noted that, the present correlation coefficient ($= 0.982$) is higher than the highest correlation coefficient obtained in the previously reported multivariable regression analysis ($= 0.96$).

In addition to model testing with inbuilt data, the proposed model was further validated using a new set of experimental data, exclusive to model formulation. The new set comprises of 10 samples, which are mostly patient blood in addition to a single control sample. The corresponding parity diagram is shown in Fig. 7. High correlation coefficient ($R^2 = 0.99$) clearly indicates the general validity of the proposed model.

Fig. 6. Comparison between actual MI and predicted MI values for training (6.I), validation (6.II), testing (6.III) and overall data set (6.IV).

Fig. 7. Parity diagram for actual vs predicted MI for model formulation exclusive sample data set.

Discussion

Deviations from regular biconcave shape are significant indicator of RBC pathology. The reasons may be genetic, infectious or chemical imbalance. For example, spherocytes or near spherical shape derivatives of RBC impede blood flow resulting in anemia, fatigue and splenomegaly²⁷. Therefore RBC deformability is regarded as a key to circulation. The biconcave shape of discocyte and related elastic properties, necessary for large, reversible elastic deformation during microcirculation in small capillaries are maintained by a variety of factors. This includes membrane lipid-lipid, lipid-protein as well as protein-protein interactions²⁸. Poikilocytic changes involve alteration of lipid raft and/or changes in interactions between anchoring and cytoskeletal proteins. Recent finding²⁹ suggests that band 3 alterations can precede and regulate the area of the outer lipid raft, relative to inner one and thus leads to a change in membrane curvature. In addition to that, disruptions of vertical (connection of integral and peripheral protein to spectrin network) and horizontal (binding of two dimensional spectrin network) interactions are known to affect the spectrin network, which invariably causes morphological alterations. The mechanical integrity of the cell structure can be estimated by shear modulus and bending modulus³⁰.

From the experimentally measured data of these two parameters, Li *et al.* have established the biconcave shape to be the only feasible minimum energy configuration³¹. Neglecting the contribution of strain energy, the biconcave shape can also be achieved by minimization of bending energy³². In the hierarchy of low energy configurations, echinocyte, stomatocyte and spherocyte appears next to biconcave discocyte as stable shape derivatives. Recent studies also postulate three major factors that influence the structure and mechanical integrity of RBC morphology as (i) shear stress, (ii) nature of vertical interactions and (iii) metabolic activity arising out from chemical energy³³.

Now a day we have highlighted techniques for studying RBC deformability. Due to various test techniques developed in the last decade, our understandings on pathophysiology of RBC have been significantly improved. Recent advances have enabled the precise measurements of various biochemical properties of RBC under systematically controlled conditions that mimic complex *in vivo* physiological environments³⁴. However, in order to make a much broader impact the current throughput of cells must be enhanced to several folds, such that it becomes a routine pathology job. Several attempts were taken for this much desired rapid quantification using different techniques in different instrumental platform, of which automated cytometric analysis has its greater share. Use of scattering property to identify the RBC's morphological alteration was first initiated by Hoffman³⁵, who has used the variation property of Rayleigh scattering from a stirred suspension to describe the shape alteration of RBC. Later this technique was further reformed by several groups^{36,37} in order to extract a quasi-quantitative information about the shape and granularity. In our previous work¹, we have reported a multivariable quadratic regression model to correlate the representative scattering profiles directly to the MI value of the respective blood sample. The present work may be viewed as an extension of previous method replacing the crude regression technique by sophisticated MLP-ANN architecture. Improved correlation coefficient ($R^2 = 0.99$), compared to our previous work, establishes the gross validity of the proposed model in rapid and accurate quantification of MI.

Conclusion

A three-layer back propagation in neural network model is proposed to simulate the Morphological Index (MI), a quantifier of the mean population morphology of RBC from rapidly generable flow cytometric data. The architecture of the back propagation neural network leading to the smallest mean square error comprised of three layered ANN with tangent-sigmoid function at hidden layers with 10 neurons, and linear transfer function at output layer. Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm was chosen to train the network. ANN predicted MI values for 60 different samples were found to be in close agreement ($R^2 = 0.982$) with the experimental MI data obtained from confocal microscopy. Therefore, the proposed quantitative technique may be viewed as a novel pathological method, which may lead to the development of new diagnostic and treatment strategies for various RBC related disease.

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